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Breaking the Cycle: How Family-Friendly Policies Alleviate Work-Family Conflict and Curb Turnover Intention Among Working Women

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of work-family conflict (WFC) and family-work conflict (FWC) on the turnover intention of working women, with a focus on the buffering role of family-friendly policies (FFPs). Based on the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, the research considers both dimensions of WFC—work-to-family conflict (WFC) and family-to-work conflict (FWC)—and their distinct influence on employees' turnover intention. Data were collected from 250 female employees working in banks in Islamabad and Rawalpindi using a structured questionnaire. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) via Smart PLS-4 was employed for hypothesis testing. The findings confirm that WFC and FWC significantly increase turnover intention among working women. However, the presence of FFPs, such as flexible work arrangements and childcare support, weakens the adverse relationship between WFC and turnover intention. However, the moderating effect is not significant for FWC. These results suggest that organizations can mitigate the negative consequences of work-family conflict by implementing supportive workplace policies. The study contributes to the literature on work-life balance by offering empirical insights into the role of organizational support mechanisms in retaining female talent. Practical implications for policymakers and organizations are discussed, along with recommendations for future research.

Keywords: Work-Family Conflict, Turnover Intention, Family Friendly Policies

Introduction

Over the past several decades, women's participation in the workforce has steadily increased worldwide. However, deeply entrenched gender roles continue to place significant burdens on working women, particularly those balancing professional responsibilities with caregiving duties. This dual pressure often results in work-family conflict (WFC), which Greenhaus & Beutell (1985) define as "a form of inter-role conflict in which the role pressures from the work and family domains are mutually incompatible." WFC manifests in two dimensions: work-to-family conflict (WFC), where job demands interfere with family obligations, and family-to-work conflict (FWC), where familial responsibilities hinder work performance (Frone et al., 1992).

Consistent with past researches, it must be noted that conflict between these two domains rises when work and family roles collide with each other. A study stated that the pressure

arising due to this collision include spending more time in work or family life, stressors within the work and/or family domains and more participation in work and/or family activities (Frone et al., 1997). Because of the interdependence of work and family, this conflict between work and family may also be considered as a source of stress that influences various withdrawal behaviors (Drummond et al., 2017). With the rise in this conflict, the employees tend to shift from short-term withdrawal such as lateness and absenteeism to long-term withdrawal behavior such as turnover. These withdrawal behaviors can affect the discipline of the organizations, add on to dysfunctional customs and ultimately increase costs to the organization (Allen et al., 2020). Keeping in line with this argument, it is significant to know how these two-dimensional work-family conflicts affect the withdrawal behaviors and what strategies can be devised in order to control or reduce these behaviors.

In response to these consequences of two-dimensional work-family conflicts, organizations have taken up several family-friendly policies (FFP) to trim down these conflicts and its consequences (Taheri, 2021). These FFP include day-care centers, job sharing and paid leave etc. The availability of these policies brings about positive outcomes that include increasing job satisfaction and low turnover intentions (Kumar et al., 2023). Past researches also show that allowing the employees to work for reduced hours or job sharing can be associated with low withdrawal behaviors (Cho & park, 2024). Furthermore, it has also been identified that the availability of onsite day-care centers lessens the turnover intentions of the employees and offering flexible work hours can lead to employee retention (Haines et al., 2024).

Previous studies have focused upon the relationship of two dimensional work family conflicts with various outcomes on the basis of stress theories where work to family conflict and family to work conflict have been studied as stressors (Liang et al., 2024; Allen et al., 2020). However, very few of the previous studies have focused on the resources, which organizations can provide to its employees through which the negative effects of these stressors can be mitigated (Chen & Fellenz, 2024).

Past researches have extensively studied consequences and antecedents of work family conflict on the basis of stress theories whereas family friendly policies (FFP) have been taken into account in various studies under the exchange theory (Bajaba et al., 2022;

Liang et al., 2024). In some previous studies, family friendly policies have been studied either as an independent variable where the focus was upon family friendly policies as an antecedent of work family conflict (Scheiman et al., 2021) or it has been studied as a dependent variable where characteristics of organizations that offer FFP to their employees was taken into account (Llanos et al., 2023). However, FFP has rarely been studied as a moderator to examine its differentiating impact on the relationship of two dimensional WFC with various outcomes. The main contribution of this study is that building on the Job Demands-Resources model, it will shed light on the missing link where FFP is neither an independent variable nor a dependent variable rather it has a buffering role to mitigate the negative effects of the two-dimensional conflict on employee turnover intention.

Theoretical Background

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model

This study is grounded in the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, which serves as a foundational theoretical lens to examine the interplay between job demands, job resources, and employee outcomes. The JD-R model focuses that every job has its own explicit working characteristics that can be divided into two broad categories i.e. job demands (e.g., work overload and cognitive demands) and job resources (e.g., autonomy and feedback). This model can be used in a number of different occupations regardless of their specific demands and resources involved. The main postulates of this model entail that high job demands and limited job resources altogether give rise to job strain. Whereas, when job resources are also high against high job demands, work engagement is experienced.

The JD-R model comprises of two hypotheses: the additive hypothesis and the buffering hypothesis. The additive hypothesis states that high job demands and low job resources lead to high job stress (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Whereas, the buffering hypothesis focuses that job resources may mitigate the adverse effects of job demands on employee wellbeing (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Therefore, building on this understudied buffering hypothesis of JDR model, along with job control and social support, this study aims to see the buffering effects of family supportive policies (job resource) on the relationship of two dimensional work family conflict (stressors) with the

employee turnover intention (outcomes) among employed mothers.

Hypothesis Development

Work-family conflict has been widely recognized as a significant stressor that adversely affects employee outcomes, particularly in occupations that require a high level of commitment and responsibility (Abdou et. al, 2024). Employees experiencing work-family conflict often struggle to balance competing demands, leading to heightened stress levels and dissatisfaction (Obrenovic et. al, 2020). Consequently, they may seek alternative employment opportunities that offer a more favorable work-life balance. Based on this, it is hypothesized as:

H1: Work-family conflict (WFC) is positively related to turnover intention among working women.

The strain that results from the interference of family responsibilities with work demands, known as Family-Work Conflict (FWC), is characterised by role excess, emotional exhaustion, and work disengagement (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). The phenomenon of FWC is especially evident among working women because of cultural expectations and gender stereotypes that frequently designate them as primary carers (Obrenovic et. al, 2020). As a result, FWC is hypothesized to have a significant positive relationship with turnover intention, implying that as FWC increases, the likelihood of women considering leaving their jobs also rises.

H2: Family-Work Conflict (FWC) is positively related to turnover intention among working women.

The presence of FFPs can act as a moderating factor by reducing the negative impact of WFC on employee withdrawal behaviours, despite the fact that work-family conflict increases turnover intention (Abdou et. al, 2024). Employees who benefit from FFPs may find it easier to manage work demands without compromising their family responsibilities. This results in lower stress levels and a reduced likelihood of seeking alternative employment hypothesized as:

H3: Family-friendly policies (FFPs) moderate the relationship between work-family conflict (WFC) and turnover intention, such that the negative effect of WFC on turnover intention is weaker when FFPs are available.

Unlike WFC, family-work conflict originates from personal or societal expectations and

family obligations. When employees experience high FWC, they may feel stressed and overwhelmed, increasing their likelihood of leaving the organization (Yao et. al, 2024). However, when FFPs—such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave, and childcare support—are available, employees receive the necessary support to balance their work and family responsibilities more effectively (Obrenovic et. al, 2020). Therefore, FFPs serve as a buffer, mitigating the adverse effects of FWC on turnover intention and helping organizations retain employees. Thus, we hypothesize:

H4: Family-friendly policies (FFPs) moderate the relationship between family-work conflict (FWC) and turnover intention, such that the negative effect of FWC on turnover intention is weaker when FFPs are available.

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model

Methodology

The data were collected from women working in Islamabad and Rawalpindi banks. A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. We distributed 285 questionnaires, out of which 250 were suitable for analysis. Some respondents didn't complete the questionnaire properly therefore, the final sample size was (N = 250). The respondents of the present study were all female. The average age of respondents was 33 years, and the average organizational tenure was 07 years. Respondents were well-educated, with most holding a bachelor's degree or higher. The job of working women in the banks is very tough and collecting data from them was a difficult task. This is a quantitative study, therefore we followed the positivism paradigm and used a deductive approach. Data collection was done by using standardized scales from past literature.

Moreover, the present study is cross-sectional, and a purposive technique was used to collect the data. Structural equation modeling (SEM) using Smart PLS-4 software was used for data analysis.

Measures

Before collecting the data, consent was taken from respondents and a brief introduction of the study was given to them. Work-family conflict and Family-work conflict were measured by the instrument developed by (Netemeyer et al., 1996). This instrument consists of 10 items. There are five work-family related items. A sample item is “The demands of my work interfere with my home family life”. Similarly, there are five family-work related items. A sample item is “The demands of my family or spouse interfere with work-related activities”. The responses were taken on 5 point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree). Turnover intention was measured using a 3-item scale by Mobley, Horner, and Hollingsworth (1978). A sample item is “I think a lot about leaving the organization”. Family-friendly policies were measured using a 7-item scale such as “flexi time” adapted from the WERS 2011 Survey of Employees (Van et. al, 2013). It is the most commonly used instrument for measuring family-friendly policies. There were four variables in the present study (Work-family conflict, Family-work conflict, Family-friendly policies, and Turnover intention). The variables are unobserved/latent; therefore, Structure Equation Modeling technique was employed to test the model. The results are presented in the next section.

Results

In this study, the data were collected from female employees working in Islamabad/Rawalpindi banks. Descriptive statistics values such as mean, standard deviation (SD), and correlations among variables have been presented in Table 1. Further, the diagonal values (in bold) are the square root of AVE values. As shown in table-1, the correlation between (WFC and TI = 0.488), the correlation between (WFC and FWC = 0.182), and the correlation between (FWC and TI = 0.481). Further, the correlation of FFP with other variables is negative.

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations, And Correlations Among Constructs

		Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1.	FFP	3.529	0.963	0.846			
2.	FWC	3.240	0.992	-0.096	0.851		
3.	TI	3.284	1.008	-0.212	0.481	0.869	
4.	WFC	3.319	0.993	-0.206	0.182	0.488	0.872

Square root of the AVE value on the diagonal (in bold) and off-diagonal values are correlations between the constructs.

In this study, we used a variance-based structural equation modeling technique using SMART-PLS 4 software for data analysis. The measurement model results are presented in Table 2. The value of Cronbach's alpha for FFP was 0.934, for FWC was 0.905, for TI was 0.838, and for WFC was 0.921. The value of CR for FFP was 0.946, for FWC was 0.929, for TI was 0.903, and for WFC was 0.941 (see Table 2). Further, the AVE value for FFP was 0.715, for FWC was 0.725, for TI was 0.756, and for WFC was 0.76. The standardized outer loadings should be 0.708 or higher (Hair et al., 2022). The outer loadings for all 20 items were greater than the recommended values of 0.708.

Table 2: Loadings/Cronbach Alpha/Composite Reliability/Average Variance Extracted

Latent Variables	Indicators	Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	Average variance extracted (AVE)
	FFP1	0.868			
	FFP2	0.844			
FFP	FFP3	0.837	0.934	0.946	0.715
	FFP4	0.850			
	FFP5	0.858			
	FFP6	0.823			
	FFP7	0.840			
	FWC1	0.850			
	FWC2	0.863			

FWC	FWC3	0.841	0.905	0.929	0.725
	FWC4	0.854			
	FWC5	0.849			
	TI1	0.885			
TI	TI2	0.855	0.838	0.903	0.756
	TI3	0.867			
	WFC1	0.883			
	WFC2	0.878			
WFC	WFC3	0.857	0.921	0.941	0.76
	WFC4	0.862			
	WFC5	0.879			

Note: FFP = Family Friendly Policies, FWC = Family-Work Conflict, TI = Turnover Intention, WFC = Work-Family Conflict

We used two methods for establishing the discriminant validity. First, the Fornell-Larcker criterion was used (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The square root of each construct's AVE should be greater than its highest correlation with any other construct. In Table 1, the square root of AVE values (bold in diagonal) is greater than its correlation with other constructs. Second, we used the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) criterion for establishing discriminant validity as proposed by (Henseler et al., 2015). The HTMT results are presented in Table 3. The HTMT values were below 0.85.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (HTMT Criterion)

	1	2	3	4
1. FFP				
2. FWC	0.102			
3. TI	0.235	0.552		
4. WFC	0.222	0.200	0.554	

Hypotheses Testing

In this study, the R² value for TI was 0.414. It indicated that 41.4 % variation in TI was explained by latent variables including WFC, FWC, and FFP (see Fig 2). The results show that WFC with TI ($\beta = 0.471$, $t = 7.618$) was positive and statistically significant,

thus supporting H₁ (see Table 4). Similarly, FWC with TI ($\beta = 0.414$, $t = 7.286$) was positive and statistically significant, thus supporting H₂. Next, we examined the moderating effect of FFP. The interaction effect ($\beta = -0.114$, $t = 2.153$) was statistically significant, thus supporting H₃. It indicates that FFP moderates between WFC and TI. However, the interaction effect H₄ ($\beta = 0.021$, $t = 0.384$) was insignificant.

Table 4: Results of the PLS-SEM Model

Hypothesis	Hypothesis Path	Path coefficient	T-value	Accept/Reject
H ₁	WFC -> TI	0.471	7.618	Accept
H ₂	FWC -> TI	0.414	7.286	Accept
H ₃	FFP x WFC -> TI	-0.114	2.153	Accept
H ₄	FFP x FWC -> TI	0.021	0.384	Reject

Note: FFP = Family Friendly Policies, FWC = Family-Work Conflict, TI = Turnover Intention, WFC = Work-Family Conflict

Figure 2: Interaction Effect Model

—————▶ : Direct effect - - - - -▶ : The moderating effect

Figure 3: Interaction Effect Diagram (FFP x WFC -> TI)

In Figure 3, FFP moderated between WFC and TI. The interaction effect is significant. However, in fig-4, the interaction effect is insignificant.

Figure 4: Interaction Effect Diagram (FFP x FWC -> TI)

Finally, we presented PLS Predict results in table-5. We assessed the predictive power of a model by using the PLS predict procedure (Shmueli et al., 2016; Shmueli et al., 2019). Results show that $Q^2_{predict}$ values are greater than 0. Further, all the PLS_RMSE values are less than LM_RMSE values. This indicates that the model has high predictive power.

Table-5: PLS Predict

	$Q^2_{predict}$	PLS_RMS E	PLS_MA E	LM_RMS E	LM_MA E
TI₁	0.313	0.979	0.796	1.018	0.821

TI₂	0.27	0.981	0.782	1.016	0.806
TI₃	0.292	0.972	0.774	1.026	0.822

Discussion

The findings of this study provide significant insights into the relationship between work-family conflict (WFC), family-work conflict (FWC), and turnover intention (TI) among working women in the banking sector, with a particular focus on the moderating role of family-friendly policies (FFPs). The results reveal that both dimensions of work-family conflict significantly contribute to turnover intention, reaffirming previous research that suggests work-life imbalances negatively impact employee retention. Specifically, work-family conflict exerts a stronger effect on turnover intention, indicating that job demands interfering with family responsibilities are a primary source of stress for working women. Hypothesis 1 and 2 predicted that work-family conflict and family to work conflict is positively related to employee turnover intention respectively. The results confirmed these hypotheses, showing that both forms of conflict significantly increase employees' inclination to leave their organizations. This is parallel to the past research indicating that both stressors result in increased employee exhaustion and burnout that leads to increased turnover intentions. The stronger impact of WFC on turnover intention highlights that the inability to manage workplace demands effectively leads to greater dissatisfaction and withdrawal behaviors among working women.

Hypothesis 3 predicted that the availability and use of family friendly policies moderates the relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention. The findings of the study confirm this hypothesis, suggesting that FFPs act as a protective factor against the negative consequences of WFC. Despite facing high levels of work family conflict, employees who had access to such policies experienced less turnover intention. These policies include job sharing, work from and flextime. In the line of this argument, this finding strengthens the notion that organizational support mechanisms play a vital role in retaining employees by mitigating workplace stressors and improving job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 4 examined the moderating effect of FFPs on the relationship between FWC and turnover intention. The findings of this study did not confirm this hypothesis, indicating that FFPs did not significantly buffer the relationship between family work

conflict and turnover intention. This posits that while organizational policies can lessen the demands from work to family but they may not adequately address the reverse phenomena that is family demands hindering work related factors. This lack of significance could be attributed to the fact that family-related demands often originate from personal and societal expectations rather than workplace policies. Future research should explore additional moderating variables, such as spousal support or domestic assistance, that might better explain the impact of family-work conflict on turnover intention.

From the results, it has been found that working mothers employed in banks have to juggle the demands from both family and work. This causes them to face the two dimensional work family conflicts that ultimately affect their productivity at work. As the two dimensional work-family conflicts increase, employees shift from temporary withdrawal behaviors (i.e. employee lateness and absence) to permanent withdrawal behavior (i.e. turnover intention). Consistent with the past researches, the results show that young working mothers who have children less than the age of 10, tend to be late or remain absent from work. However, the ones who have domestic help at home face less work-family conflict as it shares their burden of family role. The category of working mothers, who are divorced, separated or widowed being the sole bread earner had to face more work-family conflict as they do not have their spouse's support for looking after their family.

Practical Implications

The results of this study provide actionable insights for organizations, particularly in the banking sector, to enhance employee retention through supportive workplace policies.

Organizations should extend policies beyond flexible work arrangements to include on-site childcare, parental leave, and financial support for caregiving. These measures can mitigate WFC and reduce employee turnover. Supervisors should be trained to recognize the challenges faced by working mothers and encouraged to adopt family-supportive leadership styles. Supportive managers can significantly reduce work-family stress by allowing greater flexibility and understanding of employee needs. Instead of one-size-fits-all policies, organizations should implement customized work arrangements tailored to the unique needs of employees. This includes options such as remote work,

compressed workweeks, and job-sharing programs. Many employees are unaware of the FFPs available within their organizations. Clear communication and accessibility to these policies can improve utilization rates, enhancing their effectiveness in reducing work-family conflict. Encouraging a culture that normalizes the use of FFPs without stigma can lead to increased policy adoption and create a more supportive work environment for all employees.

Future Research Directions

While this study provides valuable insights, several areas require further investigation. Given that work-family conflict and turnover intention evolve over time, future research should employ a longitudinal design to examine causal relationships more accurately. This study focused on the banking sector; however, future research could explore different industries, such as healthcare and education, to compare the effectiveness of FFPs across diverse work environments. Future studies should consider other potential moderating variables, such as organizational culture, job autonomy, and spousal support, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of factors that influence the work-family conflict-turnover intention relationship. While this study focused on working women, future research could compare the experiences of male and female employees to examine whether FFPs impact them differently. A qualitative approach could provide deeper insights into employees' lived experiences with work-family conflict and the effectiveness of organizational policies in mitigating stressors.

By addressing these areas, future research can further contribute to the development of policies that promote work-life balance and enhance employee retention, particularly for working mothers navigating the complexities of career and family responsibilities.

Conclusion

This study adds more knowledge to the literature by empirically validating the buffering effect of availability and use of family friendly policies on the relationship of two-dimensional WFC and employee turnover intention among working women in the banking sector. The findings approve that WFC and FWC are significant antecedents of turnover intention, with WFC having a stronger impact. The study also highlights the effectiveness of FFPs in reducing turnover intention, though their influence varies

depending on the type of conflict experienced. Working women are an asset for a country and their talent gets suppressed when they have to juggle the demands between family and work. They experience extreme time pressure, responsibility and other difficulties in fulfilling their family and work role in time. An unbalance between family and work role becomes stressful and lead to negative work-related outcomes. Therefore, to uphold their talent and use that in a productive manner, organizations have to devise such working plans and strategies through which they can help keep these working mothers a balance between their family and work. Consequently, examining the impact of these strategies (FFP) becomes important. These findings emphasize the need for organizations to implement targeted interventions to support female employees, particularly those with caregiving responsibilities. By addressing the structural and cultural barriers that exacerbate work-family conflict, organizations can create more inclusive workplaces that foster employee well-being and retention. The study also opens new avenues for further exploration into additional moderating variables that could strengthen or weaken the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention.

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